

Original Article

TRADE ASSOCIATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT OF PUBLIC RELATIONS IN NIGERIA: FROM INFORMATION MANAGEMENT TO REPUTATION MANAGEMENT

¹Okoye, Jude Vitalis Chukwudi. (PhD) and ²Joseph O. Obi

¹Department of Mass Communication, Paul University, Awka, Anambara State, Nigeria.

²Department of Accountancy, Paul University, Awka, Anambara State, Nigeria.

E-mail: okoyejudevc2018@gmail.com, obisom64@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20210027>

Abstract: This study examined paradigm shift in public relations strategies of two maritime trade associations in Nigeria, focusing on the associations' use of public relations and shift in paradigm in public relations management. This is with the view to determining whether the associations' uses of public relations' strategies have shifted from the practice of mere information management to reputation management. Reputation management is a more systematic, strategic and evidence-based/data driven management of public perceptions of organizations. The study anchored on the individual differences theory; the theory of media preferential encoding and active audience deferential decoding of the limited media effect paradigm; and the Social accountability theory. The study sought to find out the extent the organizations used public relations; the strategies they used; the tools they used to create understanding; the prospects and challenges they faced. The study obtained data using the In-depth interview design, considering the smallness of the study's population, analyzing the data via narrative interpretation. The study found that the associations used public relations intensively, but to a limited extent, for public information disseminations, publicity, and advocacy, in a very dynamic business environment. The study found also that the organizations used media relations; identity and image management strategy; government relation and internal communication strategies. These strategies used more of one-way manipulative communication tools, especially press releases and advertorials, which hardly created mutual understanding with publics. The study found again the associations' conceptualization of public relations communication to be one-way and manipulative. The study could not establish any paradigm shift from information management to reputation management. The study therefore concluded that the associations' public relations practices had not "stamped Nigeria's public relations' 'DNA' on the global public relations timeline by shifting to a more strategic and systematic approach of managing public perceptions through relationship management.

Keywords: Public relations. Management. Strategy. Paradigm shift. Associations. Nigeria

Introduction

Good corporate performance precedes publics' recognition, which publicity seeks to achieve (Seitel, 2004). As a consequence, the best public relations campaign in the world cannot build trust while reality is damaging it.

Original Article

Reality limits what public relations can accomplish (Seitel, 2004, pg. 104). However, creating public trust and maintaining it, which is at the heart of public relations work, is a function of influencing the public relations process. The public relations process has been described as one that involved research, planned program of action, communication, and evaluation -RACE (Osho, 2008; Nkwocha, 2005; John Marston, 1963). In order to influence the public relations process therefore, public relations practitioners deliberately design most of the public relations programs, to: either: Persuade people to change their opinions on an issue, person, product, or organization; crystallize uninformed or underdeveloped opinions, or reinforce existing opinions (Seitel, 2004).

Public opinion, like Public relations that seeks to influence it, was difficult to define. It represents an expression of public perception and attitude which could manifest in symbolic form or behavior (Seitel, 2004).

Nonetheless, in engineering behavioral change, the role of attitude is essential. Attitude is very difficult to change once it had been formed (Akinfeleye, 2008). To underscore the importance of public opinion in a democratic society, American statesman, Thomas Jefferson, said that public opinion was the basis of democracy, and as such its channels of formation, the media, must be kept right (Akinfeleye, 1987).

But keeping the media of public opinion right does not end in just circulating information to the publics, through the mass media channels alone. Mass media contents were only contributory factors that worked among a nexus of other psychological and social mediating processes to influence audience members' perceptions (Klapper, 1960; Okoye & Agbanu, 2025). The psychological and social mediating processes were functions of socio-cultural consciousness, driven by audience members' needs, ideas, norms, beliefs, values, etc. Hence the need for good corporate performance as a necessary condition to hold attention and aid media messages to shape public opinion.

Public relations, today, has gone beyond mere organization's efforts in publicity and has moved to informing and counseling management on public opinion, in the present dispensation (Daramola, 2008). This is to say that Public relations practice has become a conversation, a dialogue. Good performance, however, was not limited to governments and democracies alone. It was also a prerequisite in strategic management and for social control, in both private and public institutions. This was where the status of public relations as a management function became important.

Managing public opinion well in organizations necessitates a public relations approach that harps on the management of reputation (Argenti, 2009, pg. 83). This is a proactive management approach represented as taking great pains to plan, build, sustain, and defend the sum of the publics perceptions, through the practices that (1) shaped a unique identity and (2) projected a coherent and consistent set of images to the publics (Argenti, 2009). This approach was seen as establishing a separate strategic corporate communication unit that would function as a part of the entire management structure. It is a first step an organization would take, in devising a more effective and efficient public relations strategy which would have concern for public opinion and its impact on corporate success (Argenti, 2009, pg. 83).

The issue of adopting or devising a more effective public relations strategy was a subject that had attracted attention and intellectual discussions, among communication scholars and public relations practitioners. It underscored the series of paradigm shifts in public relations practice that were evidenced in public relations evolution since its inception in history, as a mere human relations tool. Even up to the days journalists were hired to handle the "flaks" fired at CEOs, till date that corporate activities were being analyzed with unprecedented scrutiny by interest groups (Argenti, 2009; Ajala, 2001, pgs. 21-22; Daramola, 2008).

Original Article

The current dimensions of public relations practice were shown to be: (a) public relations model, as reputation management. This evolved from a less effective; (b) public information management approach. (Ajala, 2001; Daramola, 2008). This represents a shift from a public relations model that was a mere technical communication function to a public relations approach that played a more strategic corporate communication role in a dynamic and turbulent corporate environment (Grunig, 2000; Argenti, 2009). This paradigm shift in public relations strategy has been observed, purely in its communication dimension, as involving a “horizo-vertical communication pattern, which placed both the communicator and the communicatee at the same frequency and wavelength” (Akmfeleye, 2007). This is in other words a model that establishes a more interactive and mutually beneficial communication environment for creating public trust in the corporate environment and in democracies.

Statement of the Problem

National Association of Government Approved Freight forwarders (NAGAFF) and Association of Nigeria Licensed Customs Agents (ANLCA) were two major trade associations to which freight forwarders and their corporate businesses belong. NAGAFF was an umbrella body of the individual professional freight forwarders, while ANLCA represented corporate freight forwarding companies licensed by the Nigeria customs services as customs brokers. These bodies had similar objectives as provided in their constitutions: to protect the interests of their members, as well as that of the import/export community; to represent the industry through trade policy advocacy and activism; to help implement government trade policies, oppose obnoxious policies and corrupt practices involved in policy implementations. To achieve these goals, the associations carried out public relations activities to create corporate understanding and to manage issues.

Creating corporate understanding had been a function of corporate reputation, previous experience and cultural factors. To cultivate a good reputation, a credible identity and a positive corporate strategy were important integral parts of most public relations programs (Black, 1989, pg.1). Similarly, the practice of public relations in its most recent form had gone beyond mere publicity, and had shifted to (public relations) “accepting the responsibility of publicity, and in addition, playing the role of providing information and counsel to management on the nature and the realities of public opinion, as well as the methods by which organizations could establish policies, make decisions and take actions compatible with public interest (Daramola, 2008, pgs. 59-60). Again, public relations in Nigeria had grappled towards a more systematic and strategic approach, especially as regards the management of public perceptions of organizations and how well organizations cultivated, developed, and sustained positive relationships with relevant publics in a constantly changing environment and context (Ibraheem, et.al , 2014). Hence this study examined the public relations strategies of *NAGAFF* and *ANLCA* with a view to establishing whether they practiced just information management or had shifted to reputation management and possibly establishing the shift. This will highlight the prospects of smaller nonprofit and nongovernmental organizations, such as *NAGAFF* and *ANLCA*, and the motivations, if any for shifting from information management to reputation management. This is significant considering their less endowed resource bases, the nature of their publics and operating environments, which might not have the dynamics and motivations present in the operating environments of large profit making organizations and government institutions.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to ascertain whether trade associations in Nigeria have had shifts in paradigm in the use

Original Article

of public relations strategies, while the specific objectives include the following:

1. To ascertain the extent NAGAFF and ANLCA used public relations.
2. To ascertain the public relations strategies NAGAFF and ANLCA used.
3. To ascertain if the public relations tools NAGAFF and ANLCA used in public relations activities created mutual understanding with their publics.

Research Questions

1. To what extent did NAGAFF and ANLCA used public relations?.
2. What were the public relations strategies adopted by NAGAFF and ANLCA?
3. Did the public relations tools NAGAFF and ANLCA used in their public relations activities created mutual understandings with their publics?

Review of related literature

Theoretical frameworks

The individual differences theory, the theory of media preferential encoding and active audience deferential decoding of the limited media effect theory.

An aspect of perception theory, the individual differences theory held that individuals differed in their personal psychological organizations. It stated that attitudes, values, beliefs, were learnt in the context of experience (Folarin, 2002). That is they were constructed in the individual's socio-cultural environment. These psychological factors introduced the selectivity variables: selective exposure, attention, perception, retention, and recall. These resulted in differences in cognition and perception. The message might "hit the target" and yet accomplished nothing. In a complementary manner, the individual media audience members are not only active, but subjective in their interpretations of reality, marching the preferential encoding of the source with deferential decoding, thereby limiting the intended media effect (Hall, 1974, cited in McQuail 2010, pg. 73).

Social Accountability Theory

Two- part legal definitions of corporate social accountability exist. One was a requirement to give an account of corporate actions, either directly to the publics or via public authorities. The other was being liable to sanction if found in breach of some requirements or expectations attaching to the exercise of power. Often the term "accountability" is used interchangeably with "answerability", especially where accountability meant to have to explain, or justifies one's actions. The core reference is to a process of public scrutiny whereby the public activities (policies, programs, values and motives) of the organizations were confronted with the legitimate expectations of the society. Consequently, accountability is all the voluntary or involuntary processes by which the organizations answer directly or indirectly to the society and those immediately affected by the quality and/consequences of its actions (McQuail, 2003a, 2010; Feintuck, 1999, pg. 20).

Public relations meaning, Purpose and Function.

The exact meaning and purpose of public relations lacked consensus (Ibraheem, et.al, 2014; Daramola, 2008, pg.1). Reasons being that practitioners come from different backgrounds (Grunig, 2001; Daramola, 2008, pg. 11), and that lack of clear boundary of what should come under the rubric of public relations and on what should be its goal..., had made the exact origin of public relations elusive and definition difficult (Ibraheem, et.al, 2014). On whether public relations was about reputation, communication, or perhaps representing the outside world inside the organization, or whether public relations was part of the company that was ethics arbiter, there was a conclusion that public relations is a management function, that has the primary purpose of

Original Article

creating, sustaining, changing, and nurturing relationships, in the optimal interest of the organization and thereby change its value (Grunig, 2001). Hence, it is a function that must be managed with adequate matrices. Both “1978 Mexican statement” and John Marston’s (1963) RACE formula supported this position. Public relations helps to establish and promote goodwill and mutual understanding between an organization and its publics (Abodorin, 1995).

As a concept, understanding connotes knowledge, friendship and trust among individuals, various groups, and between parties (BBC English Dictionary). Furthermore, skilled public relations practice was in using modern methods or strategies of communication and persuasion to bridge the gap to establish mutual understanding (Black, 2011, pg.1). Understanding, however, was conditioned by reputation, previous experience, and cultural factors, and to cultivate a good reputation, a credible and a positive corporate strategy were important integral part of most public relations programs (Argenti, 2009; Black, 2011, pg.1). Repute, as intangible as it is (Kepferer, 2004), combined with employee morale were the goodwill of business (Nwosu, 2005). These valuable assets of business were established through the use of public relations strategies (Argenti, 2009; Black, 2011). To perform the public relations strategic functions today, the practitioner must understand its environment and be able to interpret it accurately for the benefit of the organization (Okereke, 1995; Daramola, 2008; Argenti, 2009). This involved opinion research on the relevant publics and analysis of key issues that would likely affect the efficient operation of the organization (Okereke, 1995). Public relations plans and executes strategic communication functions/ programmes and campaigns to achieve corporate objectives concerning the identified publics and the issues under focus. Such programmes might include elements such as publicity, promotions, press agency, lobbying, merchandising, personal selling, human relations, persuasion and communication (Daramola, 2008, pgs. 29-30); and or media relations, publications, spoken words, photography, exhibitions and trade fairs, advertising, films, video productions, conferences (Black,1989, pgs. 41-130). Others were identity and image management, corporate advertising and media advocacy, media relations, internal communication, community relations and development, corporate social responsibility (CSR), financial relations, government relations, organizing events, protocols, and crisis management (Argenti, 2009, pgs. 53-61; Nkwocha, 2005, pgs. 28-34).

Public relations as a strategic communication

Research, planning and communication are the major tools of public relations (Ajala, 2001; Marston, 1963). But communication is an equivocation, meaning that it could do and undo depending on the quality of the outcome of its information processing (Akinfeleye, 2010). Thus communication is used by all and in all situations, except that communication professionals focus on array of facets comprising the communication process and are concerned with how understanding is or (isn’t) achieved and how messages influence important personal, societal and global outcomes (Rubin, et.al, 2005, pgs. 3-4). Hence, the extent of public relations use, and the extent of the deployment of public relations communication strategies would determine the extent an organization could achieve understanding with its publics. This assertion is predicted on the reality of the completeness of communication, which is determined by the element of feedback of the communication process (Ogwezzy, 2008, pg. 19). This is where strategies (both management and communication) become imperative.

Strategic management refers to managerial decision making that relate the organization to its environment, guide internal activities, and determine organizations’ long term performance. It is “the art and science of formulating, implementing and evaluating a cross section of business decisions that enable an organization to

Original Article

achieve set objectives. It is a process that focused on all functional areas of business to achieve organizational success, bearing the environment in mind (Aluko, Olugbesan, et al, 2009). Strategy itself is the overall concept, approach, or general plan for the program designed to achieve a management goal (Osho, 2008; Cutlip, Center and Broom, 2000). Jefkins (1998) and Aluko, Olugbesan, et.al, (2009), seemed to suggest that the link between strategy and public relations is management. While public relations is a management communication function which has the purpose of creating publics' understanding and support for organization's policies and programmes (Jefkins,1998), strategy is a management tool or plan which has the goal of employing the most effective means (optimum utilization of resources) to achieve set corporate objectives (Aluko, Olugbesan, et.al, 2009). Therefore, public relations being a persuasive communication becomes a strategic communication function, when it becomes purposive or is consciously planned with an objective in mind; implemented; and evaluated to measure impact (Argenti, 2009). Going by this frame of reference, public relations strategy becomes a conscious communication effort geared towards influencing the organizations publics to follow a predetermined cause of action (Ibraheem et.al, 2014). It becomes the overall concept of organization's communication and its use to create understanding. The constantly changing and, unpredictable character of the operating environment of business is a factor that is not to be taken for granted if an organization is to survive (Argenti, 2009). Organization's relationship or communication with its critical publics is therefore made strategic through formal organizational structure that centralized all communications functions in a dedicated department.

The first part of an organization's public relations' use of strategies to perform the strategic functions, involves its enunciation of public relations policy (Osho, 2008, pg. 153), and this is the guide to managerial thinking (Aluko, et.al, 2009) on organization's public relations, its strategies and deployment. The starting point being to centralize all communication functions in a strategic business unit (PR. Dept.) with a dedicated budget and direct reporting line to the CEO (Argent, 2009, pgs. 48-50). Public relations policy therefore, is a formal philosophy, decision as per how to deal with the identified relevant and essential critical publics (Abodorin, 1995), concerning who they are, what their needs are what to communicate with them, the spokespersons, the internal and external media, the channels, and language. It defines the processes of developing the procedures and guidelines for communication, which is the basic tool of the profession (Osho, 2009, pgs. 152-153). Public relations policy also determines the strategies and tactics to use in reaching the internal and external publics.

Another important aspect of using public relations to perform strategic functions is Public relations planning. This is the first cardinal step in handling public relations programmes and campaigns of the organization as well as a major aspect of public relations' role that made it a management function (Osho, 2008, pg. 171). It is the blue print for action. It represents a set of decisions in readiness for action (Ajala, 2001; Jefkins, 1992; Akpan, 1986). Planning involves series of activities that must be articulated, organized, implemented, and evaluated to actualize the set objectives of the communication policy. Public relations planning process includes the following (Jefkins, 1998; Ajala, 2001):

1. Situation analysis/ environmental scanning- a process of research and analysis to fish out policy issues, the publics affected, their knowledge level and attitude, the suitable programme to solve the problem.
2. Setting the communication objectives to be achieved.
3. Deciding the media and media channels to reach the publics.
4. Deciding communication methods/ tactics to employ.

Original Article

5. Budgeting, in terms of timing, money, human and material resources.
6. Implementation.
7. Evaluation to measure program's success.

Ultimately public relations strategies are used in various forms, depending on organization's needs, issues involved and the publics concerned. Such strategies include methods such as (but not limited to) press releases, press kits, photo news, press statements, conferences, media interviews, corporate advertising and media advocacy on Op-ed pages. Others are lobbying, publication of newsletters, magazines, souvenirs, calendars, yearbooks, special reports, annual reports, book writing, information writing, speeches, profiles, broadcast writings, AGM, mementos, courtesy and facility visits, CSR, sponsorships, philanthropy, photo slides, protocols management, events, crisis management (Black, 1980; Daramola, 2008; Nkwoch, 2005) and many more.

So Communicating strategically is giving purpose, focus, direction and form to organization's intents and to share them with the relevant publics through managerial decision-making framework. This framework is illustrated by superimposing the strategic process on the basic elements of the communication process provided by Aristotle (the Art of rhetoric 367-347BC). This is in terms of thinking through the process of communication and expanding it to work in real life situation by superimposing the strategic process on it (Argenti, 2009).

The expanded strategic communication framework is as illustrated bellow:

Source: Adapted from Argenti (2009, pg. 40), corporate communication. MCGraw Hill. International edition.

Literature gap

Studies on use of public relations strategies by organizations in Nigeria and shift in public relations paradigm are few. These few studies (for example, Ibraheem, et.al. 2014), have only paid attention to big multinational corporations with established public relation budgets like Shell BP. None of the studies is shown to have examined paradigm shifts in public relations strategies in Nigeria in smaller less endowed organizations like trade and professional associations. This is the gap in literature that this study attempts to bridge.

Original Article

Methodology

The study was a case study. It adopted the **In-depth interview design**, with a structured interview guide administered to all the respondents. This is in consideration of the smallness of the size of the population of study (the chief executives and/their representatives) of the two trade associations. The associations were based in Apapa, Lagos in Southwest Nigeria. Data gathered from the study were analyzed qualitatively, in narrative prose. It has become acceptable in social research that the qualitative research approach operates from the interpretative stand point (Odotola, 2014). The use of case study though might not have provided a generalization that would lead to external validity (Tejumaye, 2003, pgs.88-90), but, was to explain a whole and provide real decisions managers had to make on a variety of real problems (Argenti, 2009, xi-xiii; Tejumaye, 2003; Rubin, et.al, 2005).

Presentation and Analysis of Data and Answers to Research question

RQ I: To what extent did NAGAFF and ANLCA use public relations?

Respondents from NAGAFF and ANLCA agreed that the associations used public relations intensively, as it has a very important role to play in disseminating information, managing issues and creating understanding with their publics and stakeholders. ANLCA's use of public relations, was basically concerned with monitoring and responding to policy issues and developments, as they affected the welfare of their members, clients, and the consumers of maritime services in general (Nwosu 2025). Similarly, NAGAFF used public relations to disseminate information to her members and other stakeholders in the industry, educate them on issues of mutual concern, advocate for better policies and oppose bad ones, as well as sensitize the stakeholders and the public concerning issues of public interests (Akokhia, 2025). Furthermore, respondents answered that communication is very important in what the association do, as members must be kept informed and opinion on government policies must be expressed as they affect the profession and welfare of Nigerians (Nwosu, 2025; Farinto, 2025).

In performing these public relations roles, the associations were found to have engaged in similar practices, although they differed remarkably in their modes of operation and locations of public relations units in their respective organizational structures. For example ANLCA adopted a "line and staff" organizational format, with a centralized public relations function, domiciled in the office of the national publicity secretary, who reported directly to their national president. ANLCA elects its publicity secretary from the general assembly every four years, and the person might not necessarily be a public relations expert. But, in order to bridge whatsoever gap this might have created, a special assistant on media and publicity is appointed (Farinto, 2025).

NAGAFF's public relations function on the other hand was decentralized. The office of the publicity secretary in NAGAFF did not exist in reality, but there is an appointed officer who represents that portfolio, without dedicated budget for communication functions. The officer who is designated as the publicity secretary reports to no one in particular. The public relations function is completely decentralized to the extent that dissemination of information could emanate from any unit. There was also a media consultant that works partly for the organization, with the responsibility of organizing press interviews with maritime reporters (Uche, 2025).

Data above showed intensive, but not extensive use of public relations by the associations. It could be interpreted both from conceptual and theoretical perspectives. It can imply that both organizations were aware of the important role public relations play in shaping attitudinal change and in managing social issues through information, persuasion and perhaps adjustments, in a liberal democracy and in an increasingly unpredictable

Original Article

dynamic business environment, such as the Nigerian maritime sector. The dynamism and unpredictability of the business environment since the advent of industrial revolution, its attendant urbanization, and the need for organizations' profitability and survival, had forced organizations to recognize the importance of public opinion (Argenti, 2009). However, it was one thing to have this realization and another to adhere to the admonition to keep it right (Akinfeleye, 2007), and yet another to devise appropriate strategies and tools to manage public perceptions towards a pre-determined cause of action.

The admission to intensive use of public relations also lent credence to assertion that 75% of what professional and trade associations do, fall within the domain of public relations (Black, 1989). But the uses of public relations by the two organizations as data showed were only to a limited extent of public information dissemination, publicity, and advocacy. The way the two organizations used public relations supported Daramola's (2008) submission that professional/trade associations' need to circulate information to members, among other objectives, determined their uses of public relations, it was much more significant as they showed that uses of public relations by the organizations had not pushed beyond the frontiers of the important area of public relations scholarship. Again in another sense, these limited uses of public relations were significant as they supported Grunig's and Hunt's (1984) work, cited in Ajala (2001), and in Smith (2004), that periodic shifts in public relations paradigm and uses were not mutually exclusive, as all the elements (press agency, publicity, public information, advocacy and relationships management) could be used at the same time to achieve set goals.

However, using public relations solely for information dissemination, publicity, and advocacy as were the cases with the organizations under study, was not completely mindful of humanizing communication by making it deliberative or by intensifying efforts to create meanings with all critical publics through dialogue, as meaning is the basic imperative of human communication (Moemeka, 2000). In other words these associations had not been mindful of managing public perceptions using a more systematic and strategic approach, especially with regards to cultivating, developing and sustaining positive relationships with the critical publics (Ibraheem, et.al, 2014). The use of public relations strategies such as publicity, public information, and advocacy, is still a one-way communication effort (Ajala, 2001; Smith, 2004; Grunig and Hunt, 1991). Although advocacy fell within the ambit of persuasion, it is one-way asymmetric. Research was involved only to the extent of gathering relevant information for crafting messages aimed solely at convincing the receivers to follow a pre-determined cause of action (Ajala, 2001). Notwithstanding the periodic and evolutionary paradigm shifts from press agency to publicity, to public information and to advocacy, public relations remained a one-way manipulative communication, until management of public perceptions of organizations, through development, cultivation and sustenance of relationships with the critical publics came into place (Ibraheem, et.al. 2014). This one-way manipulative communication model which thrived on publicity had been adjudged wanton (Ibraheem, et.al, 2014), and theoretically deficient. It did not take into account the audience members' individual differences and predetermined attitudes, as these psychological subjectivities and contexts play important roles in perception of social realities (Okoye & Agbanu, 2025). Use of public relations as mere publicity also did not consider media effect being limited by "civic activism" and receiver's subjective perception of reality dictated by needs, interests, traditions, etc, within a socio-cultural context (Hall, 1974).

Again, the associations' uses of public relations for publicity, information dissemination and advocacy did not support the corporate social accountability theory- a process of public scrutiny whereby the public activities of

Original Article

the organization(s) were confronted with the legitimate expectations of the society, and all the voluntary or involuntary processes by which the organization(s) answered directly or indirectly to the society and those immediately affected by the quality and/consequences of its actions (McQuail, 2003A, 2010; Feintuck, 1999, Pg. 20; McQuail, 2010, Pg, 206).

Equally significant was that in real practice there was a flaw in professionally structuring and organizing public relations functions in the two organizations. It was interesting to note that the associations engaged in similar public relations' practices, but showed remarkable differences in their performances and strategic locations of public relations units in their organizational structures. ANLCA for instance adopted a "line and staff" organizational format with an elected public relations officer, centralized public relations unit, domiciled in the office of the national publicity secretary. This officer was elected from the general assembly, and was complimented by a media and publicity adviser, who reported directly to their national president. NAGAFF on the other hand adopted a decentralized public relations function, with an ex-journalist as media adviser. Conceptually and contextually speaking, NAGAFF and ANLCA were far from the ideal. The phenomena in both associations did not completely support "periodization narrative". Periodization –narrative has it that when organizations realized the importance of public opinion in the achievement of set goals, and also recognized the negative impacts of the constantly changing business environment as well as the increasing public scrutiny of organizations' policies by the critical publics, such organizations opt for a centralized public relations function, manned not by ex-journalists (or just anybody), "hired to shield the CEOs" from the "flaks", but manned by public relations specialists (Argenti, 2009). ANLCA's effort could be considered half of the mark, while NAGAFF was completely off the mark in this regard.

Furthermore, data also indicated that public relations function in these associations had no dedicated budgets. This was an aberration, and completely negated the much taunted approach that management of public relations must be strategic by super-imposing the strategic process (including proper resource allocation) on the communication process (Argenti, 2009).

RQ II: What were the public relations strategies used by NAGAFF and ANLCA?

Data showed that the associations had a good identification of their publics/stakeholders and the strategies in place to deal with them. The publics included their members, clients who are mainly importers and exporters; the employees and management staff; the area council, communities of Apapa and Amuwo Odofin; the mass media, national, state, community and beat associations. Strategic affiliations and Alliance Partners include Nigeria Customs Services, Council for the Regulation of Freight Forwarding in Nigeria (CRFFN), International Federation of Customs Brokers Associations (IFCBA), International Federation of Freight Forwarders Associations (FIATA), Borderless Alliance, ECOWAS, Nigeria Institute of Certified Customs Brokers (NICCB), Nigeria Chamber of Shipping (NCS), Shipping Company Association of Nigeria, Ports Consultative Council, NACCIMA, Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN), Association of Bonded Terminal Operators, Nigerian Shippers Council, Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA), Maritime Reporters Association of Nigeria (MARAN), League of Maritime Editors (LME), and Seaport Terminal Operators Association of Nigeria (ANLCA's official brochure (2014, pg. 21). Similarly, NAGAFF deals with mainly the people and organizations in the maritime sector, like the Nigerian police, Nigerian Immigration service, Ministry of transport, the Executive, the Judiciary and the Legislature, Standard organization of Nigeria, NAFDAC, NDLEA, and DSS, banks, insurance companies, and port concessionaires as they formulate and implement

Original Article

policies that affect what they do(Akokhia,2025). NAGAFF, however, showed it did not always pay full attention to all its critical publics, but rather used strategies and tools of media relations; corporate identity and **image** management; internal communications; and government relations, most frequently, to address issues and to relate with the publics. It used the press as the mouth pieces to educate those in the maritime sector.

Data above were significant in many ways as they indicated that the associations were dealing with very sophisticated and active publics. The publics were many and varied. It then implied that employing vibrant civic activism to deal with such publics could not be ruled out in their responses to issues of public concern. Data also showed that the strategies adopted to deal with these many and varied publics were mainly media relations, complimented with corporate identity and image management, internal communications, and government relations. This again implied that there was no other strategic public relations function in place to help manage the other identified publics. It then meant that the strategic interests of these other publics were neglected. For example, as important as the local community and the physical environment were, there was no specific strategic function in place to deal with them. Contextually, this fact did not go in line with the current trend that public relations in Nigeria was becoming strategic and grappling towards management of public perceptions of organizations and how well organizations cultivate, develop, and sustain positive relationships with relevant and critical publics in a constantly changing environment and context (Ibraheem, et.al, 2014).

Again using predominantly media relations strategy to address all the publics, ignored context, which is the basis for meaning. This also meant that the neglected publics would not recognize or perceive the associations in good light. This fact gave credence to the assertion that reality destroys what public relations can accomplish, since performance goes before recognition (Seitel, 2004). Emphasis on the use of public relations for information dissemination and publicity rendered the associations' use of public relations mere one-way effort and a matter of using the mass media as the sole means of reaching everybody and anybody. Even the practice of media relations by the associations had nothing "relationship" to show. Press releases were shown to be sent to media organizations without media research, full understanding and close media partnership that should be the hallmark of media relations. Again total dependence on the mass media to deal with the greater percentage of the associations' publics did not recognize the fact that while the media preferentially encode messages, the active media audiences differentially decode them, based on their contexts and subjective perceptions of reality (Hall, 1974). This might be why there exists a major challenge of the associations not getting their publics to shift from their pre-conceived positions (Akokhia, 2025). The strategies used by the associations in many cases were not adequate to deal with such active publics in such a dynamic environment.

RQ III: Did public relations tools NAGAFF and ANLCA used in their public relations activities created understanding with the publics?

The two associations showed that they were dealing with active and sensitive publics, as well as operating in a very dynamic socio-cultural environment. But concerning the use of social research as a public relations tool, the two associations' claimed to have always used formal opinion and attitude research findings as guides to their public relations activities, turned anecdotal. They could not provide any specific factual evidence of having done an empirical study of any sort about their strategic publics, including media research.

On the question of what their public perception was, for example, Akokhia (2025) said that the publics think highly of NAGAFF, though not based on empirical data, but based on the association's antecedents and its position in the Nigerian maritime industry.

Original Article

Communication audits revealed that the organizations used the public relations tools of press release most frequently, radio jingles, branded items, corporate names, corporate colors, logos, flags and corporate architectures to attract and keep public attention and to create prestige. The associations have also used events and media interviews to give out information. Most the events were media events targeted at the print and electronic media, (especially the local and community based media) as well as posts on the internet and the social media networks. Their CEO'S also in some cases appeared on radio talk show programs, and granted interviews for newscasts on burning policy issues. The associations also engaged in lobbying government officials and policy makers, especially Nigerian customs, as part of government relations strategy. They used issue advocacy and corporate advertising, as well as advertorials and media advocacy on broadcast media and print op-ed pages to sensitize the citizenry and conscientize the policy makers. Communication audit also indicated that they used public notices, bill boards, and speeches, courtesy calls and visits, circulars, memos, meetings, phone calls, announcements, e-mails, bulk SMS, websites and social media platforms, especially for internal communication. Investigation further revealed that the two associations published newsletters: "Customs Agent by ANLCA and "Total Transport" by NAGAFF. Enuma (2025), said that "Total Transport" has an interactive online web page hosted on Facebook, but had stopped publishing its hard copy version due to lack of qualified staff and fund. Again, he said that the web page was not frequently updated because they had no designated staff in charge. The associations' websites, www.anlca.org.nig, and www.nagaff.org, as investigation revealed were functional but not frequently updated.

On public relations evaluation, no single evidence of conscious effort for programs evaluation, whether on-going or after-project evaluation. Even broadcast monitoring and press clips, very common in most public relations campaigns, were not done. There was no evidence of formal evaluation research on public relations programs and campaigns in the two associations.

Data above have many implications for the Associations' practices of public relations. It was a paradox that the two associations dealt with very active, sophisticated and sensitive publics, and operated in a very dynamic environment, and yet did not use social research as a public relations tool. Data showed that they did not use formal opinion and attitude research findings as guides to their public relations activities. There were no evaluations either. Conceptually this was completely out of place. The meaning of this is that the associations' public relations communications were intangible as they excluded formal planning and measurement of effectiveness through feedbacks from policy research and evaluations. The implication was that public relations efforts of these associations ended up as incomplete communications (monologues), and hence lacked the capacity to create mutual understanding with the publics. The feedback element of the communication process (which formal research offers), makes communication complete (Ogwezzy, 2008). Research makes public relations evidence-based, responsible, and a hallmark of relationship management that helps to create understanding with the target publics, especially as regards the management of public perceptions of organizations and how well organizations cultivate, develop, and sustain positive relationships with relevant publics in a constantly changing environment and context (Ibraheem, et.al, 2004). The practice of public relations in its most recent form had gone beyond mere publicity, and has shifted to (public relations) accepting the responsibility of publicity, and in addition, playing the role of providing information and counsel to management on the nature and the realities of public opinion, as well as the methods by which organizations could establish policies, make decisions and take actions compatible with public interest

Original Article

(Daramola, 2008).

Furthermore, it was significant to note that such tools as press releases, jingles, corporate names, logos, colors, flags, corporate branding, corporate architectures, branded items and others, that were frequently used, nonetheless, had conceptual and theoretical meanings and implications to point at from communication perspective. Of course using the tools were in line with Jefkins (1989), Black (1989), and Grunig (2001), but the extents these tools created mutual understanding with the associations' publics were suspect. The most obvious implication was that the tools were more of one-way manipulative communication tools, characterized by "dumping information" on the publics (Moemeka, 2000). Such tools had also been found wanton (Ibraheem et al, 2014). The associations' conceptualization of communication as indicated by these tools, had several weaknesses which presented challenges to communication and reduced the prospects of achieving mutual understanding, for the reasons that they were "linear and one-way rather than circular and two-ways. They led heavy emphasis on the communicator rather than the receiver; ignored the context, which in point of fact provides the bulk of the meaning of communication; gave the pride of place to manipulation over mutuality and reciprocity; perceived individuals as atomistic entities as opposed to interacting elements in a collectivist and communalistic system; and treated communication in a mechanical rather than organic terms (Moemeka, 2000). In contrast, conceptualization of modern communication is interaction in a specific socio-cultural context through shared meanings or feedback (Moemeka, 2000; Ogwezzy, 2008). This all important goal of being on the same "frequency and wave length" with the publics (Akinfeleye, 2007), would not be achieved because of lack of dialogue (listening\conversation), and because they were predicted on organization's performances, and revealed through opinion research. These are the hallmarks of public relations strategies and keys to creating mutual understanding. Tools used by these associations therefore, would certainly not create mutual understanding. At best they served as tools of modernized town crying.

Summary of findings

The study found as follows, that:

1. The associations used public relations intensively, but to a very limited extent, especially for information disseminations, publicity, and advocacy, in a very dynamic business environment, with varied and active internal and external publics.
2. The public relations strategies used were media relations, identity and image management, government relations and internal communication only.
3. The tools were dominated by information management (one-way manipulative communication) tools that do not create mutual understanding, but used to engineer public consents, manipulate and control public opinion.
4. Apart from ANLCA which had a centralized public relations function in a "staff and line" organizational structure that could be closely associated with the global best practice, NAGAFF had a decentralized public relations function that is completely off the mark.
5. The use of research of and in any form to drive the public relations efforts, including programmes planning and evaluations were lacking.
6. Conceptualization of public relations communication was faulty and nature of communication was one-way, lacking in feedback and dialogue.
7. The two organizations had no formal public relations planning, as well as budgets and were seriously

Original Article

hampered by the challenges of funds and qualified public relations staff. This limited professionalism and excellence in their public relations practices.

8. Conclusion

It was evident from the above findings that the extent NAGAFF and ANLCA used public relations, and the strategies and tools they used to create understanding, were less of the functions of active publics, dynamic and unpredictable environment, but more of the functions of the organizations' public relations objectives, conceptualization of communication, availability of funds, and level of professionalism. The organizations, public relations objective was manipulation. Conceptualization of communication, strategies and tools adopted, were one-way manipulative and top-down. Lack of funds, absence of research and evaluation constituted big challenges and public relations professionalism and excellence were almost non existence. Considering that the focus of this study was to determine whether the trade associations: (NAGAFF and ANLCA) have in their public relations practices, shown any paradigm shift from information management to reputation management, this study could not establish any real -shift in public relations paradigm from mere information management to reputation management. This study concluded that the uses of public relations by these trade associations had not pushed beyond the frontiers of this important area of public relations scholarship.

Recommendations

For the associations to use public relations strategies to create mutual understanding, they must strive for public relations strategies and tools that would co-opt the publics in the scheme of public affairs, through dialogue and sense of belonging. This will help solve some of the social problems bedeviling the maritime industry in particular and Nigeria in general, especially corruption. This study therefore recommended as follows:

- NAGAFF and ANLCA should as a matter of corporate policy establish functional public relations units, with dedicated budgets, headed by trained public relations/communication specialists responsible to their presidents. This is the global best practice.
- Tools of practice should include research and evaluation, which help to create opportunities for dialogue with and feedbacks from the publics. Again this is the trend in modern public relations professional practice.
- Appropriate strategies and tools beyond media advocacy should be used to manage relationship with the identified strategic publics and to measure programmes' effectiveness.

References

- Abodorin, T.(1995). *Fundamentals of Public Relations*. Lagos: One Soul Publishers Nig Ltd
- Ajala, V. O. (2009). *Scholarly Writing Guide for Researchers*. Ibadan: Maybest Publishers.
- Ajala, V O. (2001). *Public Relations: In Search of Professional Excellence (2nd Ed.)*. Ibadan; May Best Publications.
- Akinfeley, R.A.(2008). *Contemporary Issues in Mass Media for Development and National Security*. *Lagos: Malthouse Press Ltd.*
- Akinfeleye, R.A. (2007). *Essentials of Journalism: An Introductory Text for the Beginner (3rd Ed.)*. Lagos:

Original Article

Unimedia publishers.

Akinfeleye, R.A, (2010). Unpublished complimentary Lecture Notes.

Akokhia F. (2025). Deputy National President (NAGAFF). Personal Communication. Lagos 07/08/2025.

Akpan E.D (1986). Planning Public relations campaign. In Osuji C.(ed.). Principles of Public Relations. Owerri: Opinion research and comm. Publications.

Aluko, M., Odugbesan, O., Gbadamosi, G., Osuagwu, L.(2009). Business Policy and Strategy (3rd Ed.). Lagos: Longman.

Anaeto, S. G., Onabajo, O. S., and Osifeso, J.B (2008). Models and Theories of Communication (2008). Maryland (USA): African Renaissance Book Inc.

Argenti, P. A. (2009). Corporate Communications. New York: McGraw Hill.

BBC English Dictionary (....). London: Harper Collins Publishers.

Berger, A.S.(2005). Media Analysis Techniques (3rd. Ed.). London: Sage Publications.

Black, S. (1989). Introduction to Public Relations. Lagos: West African book Publishers Ltd.

Daramola, A.C. (2008). Fundamentals of Professional Public Relations. Lagos: Certified Marketing Communications Institute of Nigeria.

Enuma Lucky (2025). Web Master, NAGAFF. Personal communication. Lagos. 07/08/2025

Farinto K. (2025), Publicity Secretary ANLCA. Personal communication. Lagos. 03/08/2025

Folarin, B. (2002). Theories of Mass Communication: An Introductory Text. Lagos: Link Publications.

Friere, P (1970). *The Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. New York: Continuum.

Grunig, J.(2001). Public Relations As A Management Function(Speech). Compiled by Olayemisi Isichei. Ikeja: Nigeria Institute of Public Relations

Grunig and Hunt(1984), cited in Smith, R.(2004). Public relations history. Retrieved from <http://faculty.buffalostate.edu/smithrd> and compiled by Isichei Yemisi (2009). NIPR Training School, Ikeja.

Ibraheem, I.A., Ogwezzy-Ndisika, A. O., Akanni, T. (2014). Shell oil as a window into the development of public relations in Nigeria in St. John III et.al. (2014). *Pathways to Public Relations: History of Public Relations Practice and Profession*. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis group.

Original Article

Jefkins, F. (1998). *Public Relations* (5th Ed.). England: Pearson Educational Ltd.

Kepferer, J. (2004). *The New Strategic Brand Management*. London: Kogan Page.

Klapper, J. (1960). Reinforcement theory (I) In Anaeto, S.G. et al. (2008). *Models and Theories of Mass Communication*. Maryland African renaissance book.

Marston J. (1963), cited in Nkwocha, J. (2005). *Effective Media Relations: Issues, Strategies and Dynamics*. Lagos: Zoom Lens Publications.

McQuail, D. (2010). *McQuail's Mass Communication Theory* (6th.Ed.). London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Moemeka, A.A. (2000). *Development Communication in Action: Building Understanding and Creating Participation*. Maryland: University Press of America.

Nkwocha, J. (2005). *Effective Media Relations: Issues, Strategies and Dynamics*. Lagos: Zoom Lens Publications.

Nwosu, E.I. Forward NIPR examination syllables. Nigerian Institute of public relations. Lagos.

Nwosu Joel (2025), Director-General ANLCA. Lagos, Personal communication. Lagos. 03/08/2025.

Odutola, K. (2014). When they came (for Olatunji Dare), in Adebawo W. (2014) *Public Intellectuals, Public Sphere and Public Spirit*, Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.

Ogwezzy, A.O. (2008). *African Communication Systems: Concepts, Channels and Messages* Lagos: African Renaissance Books Inc.

Okereke, M. (1999). *Public relations and systematic planning*. PR digest Vol. 4.

Okoye, J.V.C., Agbanu, V.N., (2025), Analysis of Select Newspapers' Representations of the three major Candidates in the February 25, 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary journal of Linguistics, Marketing and Communication*, vol. 1, no. 1, Jan-March, 2025, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14999000

Osho, S.A. (2008). *Public Relations Policy, Planning and Strategy*. Abeokuta: ESS OH Consult Publications.

Rubin, R.B., Rubin, A.M., Piele, L.J. (2005). *Communication Research: Strategies and Sources* (6th. Ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

Seitel, F.P. (2004). *The Practice of Public Relations* (9th). New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

Smith, R. (2004). *Public relations history*. Retrieved from <http://facultv.buffalostate.edu/smithrd> and compiled

Original Article

by Isichei Yemisi(2009). NIPR training school, Ikeja.

Tejumaye, A.J. (2003). *Mass Communication Research: An Introduction*. Lagos: Dapson Inter. Nig. Ltd.

Uche, I. (2025), national executive secretary NAGAFF. Personal communication. Lagos 07/08/2025.